

TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY BY MEANS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In terms of language skills, the modern curriculum at a non-linguistic university is focused on the use of language for the purpose of communication, focusing on the communicative aspect. The functionality of this approach is to create conditions for sustainable learning of foreign languages by students of non-linguistic universities through modern technologies focused on supporting feedback, motivating them for further learning. New technologies make material available to students in the form of texts, videos, audio documents and many other educational materials; the use of exercises that are specifically designed for learning a foreign language makes it possible to choose their own learning strategy and develop one that effectively improves their language skills.*

Key words: *foreign language, university, modern technologies, effective improvement of students' language skills.*

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В НЕЯЗЫКОВОМ ВУЗЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. *С точки зрения языковых навыков современная учебная программа в неязыковом вузе сосредоточена на использовании языка с целью общения, фокусируется на коммуникативном аспекте. Функциональность данного подхода состоит в том, чтобы создавать условия устойчивого изучения иностранных языков студентами неязыковых вузов посредством современных технологий, ориентированных на поддержку обратной связи, мотивируя их на дальнейшее обучение. Новые технологии делают доступным для обучающихся материал в виде текстов, видеороликов, звуковых документов и многих других учебных материалов; использование упражнений, которые специально созданы для изучения иностранного языка, дают возможность выбрать собственную стратегию обучения и развивать ту, что эффективно повышает их языковые навыки.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннный язык, вуз, современные технологии, эффективное повышение языковых навыков студентов.*

The culture of learning in the 21st century has changed. Higher education in modern society is neither a privilege nor a characteristic of certain social strata, but a necessary prerequisite for competitive professional positions in a saturated labor market.

The current generation of students is the so-called network generation, they are also experts in the use of new technologies, learning them intuitively, partly because they grew up with them.

If the educational material is relevant to the image of their own life experience - this has a positive effect on the success of learning. They can rely on a wide range of prior knowledge.

The need for knowledge of a foreign language stems from the economic and social context, so that learning and teaching can better contribute to the implementation of various plans of students. The Internet, the Web and mobile devices, other modern technologies are already indispensable in the field of teaching and learning languages. The generation of networks and forms of communication in the educational system are also activated. Paradoxically, knowledge of foreign languages and spatial unification open up enormous opportunities for individualization, making a young specialist largely independent, in terms of space and time, and contributing to independent, autonomous, constructive pragmatic education. "One of the tasks in teaching a foreign language is to identify and take into account the individual needs and abilities of students, to search for technologies for their creative development and implementation" [2].

The importance of the quality of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is that: a specialist in the context of professional communication is underestimated - i.e. there is a need to be able to present technical (scientific) content: a lawyer for his client, a doctor for his patient, a civil engineer, etc. must have professional communication skills, and they cannot express this only in technical terms.

We teach at universities the skills of language implementation, adaptation and modification, in the communication context necessary for this, and, finally, in the context of a practical way of life. Teaching practice has shown that, provided that equivalent linguistic and linguocultural knowledge is obtained, communication of graduate specialists across language barriers, orientation in a foreign culture becomes easier. In any case: it works. A non-linguistic university is a guarantor of appropriate forms of organization and teaching of an interdisciplinary foreign language, obtaining basic knowledge of intercultural skills, the possibility of functionally successful contacts with the country of the studied language.

New training programs based on new modern technologies, teaching aids containing original non-linear texts can be of great benefit both in informal and formal, institutional contexts, supporting the differentiation of teaching methods, quick organization in obtaining additional information or correction of the received one. The selection of texts from reliable sources is the first step in quality control carried out by the teacher. Corresponding to the required quality criteria, authentic texts, textbooks, modern, didactically correctly prepared online materials can be valuable sources for the development of both linguistic literacy and intercultural communicative

competence, and cultural awareness. "The selection of high-quality material for foreign language textbooks, and this is, first of all, text material, in turn, presupposes high scientific qualifications of the creators of textbooks, their presence of not only good linguistic and methodological knowledge, but also knowledge from the professional sphere of the student, since the inclusion of specialists in a specific field in the team of authors, unfortunately, occurs quite rarely" [1].

In the process of studying at a regional non-linguistic university, in a predominantly bilingual audience, work with texts in audio and video formats is stimulated to develop language competencies, for example, argumentation or opinion writing. All types of work with educational material include exercises on an interactive whiteboard, the range of which varies. This can be a chain of simple reproductive speech exercises and tasks for the implementation of small joint projects for the implementation of tasks of a communicative, intercultural-communicative and lingua-cultural nature. Their additional value lies in the fact that they are aimed at the systematic use of language tools: simple expressions and conversational-thematic models.

In order to initiate intensive interaction processes for oral speech, speech acts of a dialogical form have been developed, in which not only the content is reproduced, but also communication in a foreign language. Dialogic speech can be performed in pairs, or in group work under the control of the teacher, which stimulates interpersonal interaction between him and the students, but mainly between the students. The positive learning outcome is that students are encouraged to initiate and maintain communication in such a way as to move to a fundamentally more authentic linguistic level. This is facilitated by variable written exercises that develop written literacy and help to accelerate the acquisition of speech skills that play an important role in the written reproduction of what has been learned.

Oral and written methods of independent work of students - translations of texts, other information - should be considered as forms of stimulating the proper quality of their information awareness, in the sense of encouraging communicative readiness, popularizing the teaching of a foreign language (in our case, German), the use of different technologies and methods of work; heterogeneity of the proposed means that promote an integrative approach to individual skills; combining reading comprehension and listening comprehension of text with writing skills; their functioning as pedagogical means of communication designed to encourage students of a non-linguistic university to study languages in general, stimulate multilingual and intercultural experience and stimulate self-reflection.

The vast field of mastering foreign languages and communicating with the help of new technologies available at the university continues to develop at an accelerated pace.

There is a growing need for more sophisticated methods based on web resources that facilitate the collection and processing of information. However, although the use of modern technologies in teaching is valuable, without the supervision of a teacher it becomes a problem even for those who understand technology. For foreign language teachers, this means that continuous professional development of the teaching staff and the development of new forms of teaching and learning (e.g. blended learning), curricula and textbooks with many variable assignments are of high priority.

The modified didactic approach allows combining socially constructive perspectives of teaching a foreign language in the context of a regional non-linguistic university, providing constant, constructive feedback, thanks to which the potential learning outcome is under control. It is possible to change / adapt / vary a certain text / content formulated in a foreign language; use the technologically supported principle of "collective intelligence", since a larger number of students can usually demonstrate high-quality knowledge or competence in the process of teaching a foreign language in subject-language and cultural specific issues or problems, using the learned vocabulary, grammar, syntax, rules of argumentation, etc., to reflect, formulate contextualized content. For this purpose, a wide range of exercises is developed for repetition, consolidation and practice of foreign languages on an individual and group basis.

In the process of teaching foreign languages to students, we also use traditional language methods due to their pedagogical and didactic versatility and, in the context of blended learning, we take into account the aspect of multidirectional reflection, which enhances the cooperation between the teacher and students. Students learn to translate and critically analyze the provided text, taking into account certain aspects of grammar (sentence structure, use of time expression forms, etc.), vocabulary (use of substantively adequate words / phrases) and discursive strategies, primarily related to the didactic area, as well as the communicative area, in which more and more attention is paid to the active study of a foreign language using modern means, focusing on educational requirements and the experience of those working in this area, as a result of which "one of the ways to optimize the preparation of university students for discussions in a foreign language within the framework of the communicative approach is seen in the formation of the ability to correlate the language means and speech techniques known to students with the communicative tasks solved during the discussion. To do this, it is necessary to develop skills for the adequate use of linguistic means and speech techniques to achieve the pragmatic effect of a statement during a discussion" [4, p. 54]

Thanks to the use of mobile technologies, various models of student learning should stimulate interest in learning, because it is very interactive, characterized by a high level of

independent activity, therefore, it should contribute to success in learning. Immediate and positive feedback can have a positive impact on students' motivation to learn a foreign language and not only, especially for students with unsatisfactory indicators.

However, it is necessary to take into account the high level of responsibility of the teacher when working with new technologies, the importance of improving professional qualifications, since technical changes also offer risks. The role of the teacher changes from a knowledge broker to a learning consultant, and this presupposes didactic competence, consisting of many individual skills: from general pedagogical to technical knowledge. A constructive, pragmatic understanding of the educational process will smooth out the rather difficult process of "leaving" the traditional comfort zone of the teacher. Foreign language communication of students with each other and the teacher, in groups or teams is supported through a joint translation process, conferences, round tables, meetings, thematic events, etc. A creative approach opens up new and interesting areas of activity for the student, which he can use in his future professional activity - confidently and productively. Bilingualism is the norm in our regional society, which can give students a promising professional and personal perspective. Unfortunately, students often exaggerate their capabilities and experience unrealistic expectations of success.

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